

Family Pressure, Peer Influence, and Teenagers Involvement in Prostitution

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Abstract:

The study investigated ‘Family Pressure, Peer Influence, and Teenager’s Involvement in Prostitution’. The study area was Delta State. The target population for the study was teenagers between the ages of 15 and 18 found in some brothels, on the street at night, and in guest houses involved in prostitution as a way of surviving a hard time. The sample size is 120 teenagers. The questionnaire was developed by the researcher and validated by experts in the field of measurement and evaluation. Both instruments have a reliability of

0.78 and 0.85, respectively. An in-depth interview was conducted with six respondents; this was made possible by the participant observation method adopted by the research. A photograph was taken. A semi-structured interview guide was used for the IDI. The researcher transcribed the data acquired from the in-depth interviews through the use of a recording device, and they were compared with the notes taken by the note-taker during the meetings. Both the transcribed tapes and the field notes were utilized for data analysis. Simple regression was used to test the first two hypotheses, and multiple regression was used to analyzing the last hypothesis, as well as content analysis for the In-depth interview. Findings from the study revealed that peer influences are a major variable that propels teenagers into prostitution, and a lack of economic power has put strains on parents to send their girl child to the city in the name of searching for green pasture, who end up becoming prostitutes. A recommendation was made that parents should take full responsibility for the upbringing of their children and should desist from giving their children economic favors from friends and relatives. In most cases, such children end up becoming prostitutes and armed robbers.

Keywords: *family pressure, peer influence, teenager involvement, prostitution.*

Introduction

Prostitution, as in other parts of the world, has continued to gain ground with the proliferation of brothels and hotels for sex workers in most urban centers as well as rural areas. Ladies no longer see anything wrong with the trade as a means of economic survival. Due to the fact, that some parents can’t afford the financial capacity to further their ward’s education. Thus, some have resorted to the use of prostitution to further their education. It is prevalence in today’s

Nigerian cities seeing teenagers roaming the streets and entertainment centers seeking pertronnages when they are supposed to be in school or elsewhere learning skills.

Diverse research on teenager prostitution in different parts of the world outlines cogent reasons such as family types, vicious cycles of poverty, economic hardship, insecurity, broken homes, peer group influence, influence from the environment, lack of opportunity, and early sexual experience that largely predispose women

and girls to prostitution as an occupation to survive life realities (Olufemi & Olasunkanmi, 2015; Izugbara, 2010).

Prostitution in Nigeria is an illegal business because the law prohibits the act, but no active action has really been taken against it by the government (Onah, 2000). In various states of the nation, adolescents are seen and found engaging in prostitution as a way of feeding themselves in hotels, bars, and brothels at strategic locations at night in busy junctions. Mugane (2022) posits that teenager prostitution is carried out in hostels, brothels in the streets, or rented rooms like hotels and guest houses. This is followed by leaving their mobile phone contacts on social media and pictures in order to receive appointments on a paid or unpaid basis.

Prostitution is termed as deviance and unhealthy in society. Years ago, family members and societies frowned at those involved in business as a way of life; they were often found on the fringes of villages and towns, but in today's world, the reverse is the case. Maria (2022) is of the view that many young women and girls fall prey to pressure from poverty in their families and peer associations who see no other alternative to survival in an economically difficult situation, but commercializing the body for financial gain is the only choice available to them.

In corroborating this point, Choji (2013) noted that teenagers of secondary school age are now in competition with older women to offer their bodies to men. Similarly, Bamgbose (2002) asserted that young girls were taking over the business of prostitution from older women, who, up to that time, were the dominant practitioners. These are indications that girl prostitution is becoming an "occupation" among girls of secondary school age (Bello & Jamilu, 2016; Saphira & Oliver, 2002). However, it should be stated here that the problem of teenager prostitution is not peculiar to Nigeria, as a report released by the Global March against Child Labor showed children involved in prostitution to be in every part of the world, with Africa and Asia having the highest prevalence rates (Bamgbose, 2002).

Furthermore, because the prostitute has collected money for sex, she has conferred on the man authority and power to decide what kind of sex he will have. Such an act could be expected to endure brutality, rape, and other crimes against a female behind closed doors (Alobo & Ndifon 2014). Prostitutes have an increased incidence of sexually transmitted diseases (STDs) such as gonorrhea, syphilis, Candida, and herpes virginalis. A study by Okafor and Duru (2010) revealed that 15% of prostitutes who had prostituted for at least six months had STDs. Prostitutes are at greater risk of cervical cancer caused by the human papillomavirus contracted through sex. They are prone to having unwanted pregnancies, which makes them indulge in unsafe abortions that result in pelvic inflammatory diseases (PID). PID causes secondary infertility, which leads to broken families and their consequences. Some prostitutes suffer trauma and pelvic pains, which subject them to drug, alcohol, and smoking additions to ease off the pains, and these habits could cause cancer, which would put their lives in more jeopardy and increase the mortality rate of the country.

There are not exact statistics of teenage children engaging in prostitution factor due to the sensitivity of the subject and the difficulty of accessing the location of affected population, which makes the available statistics defective. The word prostitution refers to the act or practice of providing sexual services to another person in return for payment. The person who receives payment for sexual services is called a prostitute. Globally, there are about 40 million prostitutes at work in different places at any given moment, and 80% of the world populations into prostitutes are female, age ranging from 11–35yrs. One in ten men have in one time purchased prostitute, and men between 35 and 44yrs recorded higher in sex purchase demographically (Ede et al., 2020). In this study, teenager prostitution was defined as the sexual services rendered by a girl child of less than 18 years of age for any form of compensation, but mainly financial in nature. Evidence has shown that countless girls all over Nigeria engage in prostitution, as some girls patrol the streets

almost naked while others position themselves at strategic geographical spaces such as nightclubs and hotels, among others. Ampofo (2022) justifies such a point by saying: The lack of obtaining economic and financial support from close people like mates, partners, and relatives has forced teenagers to finally engage in prostitution. Similarly, the macroeconomic shifts and changes that cause economic constraints have also accelerated women's willingness to work as prostitutes.

In some places, people have opted to be prostitutes due to the closure of their business ventures, which has persistently fostered insufficiencies (Chakwe 2005). In addition, Yusuf (2013) submitted that there is an increase in teenage prostitution and sex-related activities among young people due to the inability of parents to meet their financial obligations. Parents may be compelled to send their female child to individuals who promise to train and educate them in return; not knowing the child will be forced into prostitution. Again, Olugbile and Adelakun (2008) wrote that peer influence is everywhere, where everyone wants to be like others and ends up prostituting. The bad girls who embrace prostitution gradually corrupt the more conservative ones. If, for example, one person had three cell phones and flashy clothes, another would want to do the same or more. For those who are probably not from very rich homes, they are forced to do otherwise. Furthermore, with the soaring inflation in the economy and being in a precarious condition, they turn to prostitution based on the fact that they are looking for money to settle their bills. While scholars have diverse opinions on what constitutes prostitution, they have come up with a considerable number of closely related factors influencing prostitution. In the internet survey conducted by Ausbeth-Ajagun (2005), such factors as poverty, parental attitude, laziness, greed, and avarice, broken homes, poor parental upbringing, deceptive media appeal, godlessness, a distorted value system, and ignorance were identified as influencing prostitution.

Adesina (2006) also identifies poverty, inadequate job opportunities, and greed as important factors, especially in Nigeria. Though

various studies have surveyed the perils of prostitution, our knowledge of teenage prostitution is limited. Hence, the study examined Family Pressure, Peer Influence, and Teenage Involvement in Prostitution in Delta State.

Theoretical Framework

The Situational Mechanism Model

The work employed "The Situational Mechanism Model," also known as the "PEA Hypothesis." The Situational Mechanism Model is the second axiom (model) of the general Situational Action Theory (SAT). The theory emerged in 2004 in the work of Per-Olof H. Wikström, titled "Crime as Alternative: Towards a Cross-level Situational Action Theory of Crime Causation". The theory presented a general, dynamic, and mechanism-based explanation of crime and deviance, analyzing crime within the standpoint of moral actions.

SAT is a grand theory that can cogently explain nearly all actions defined as crimes (general view of crime), focuses on the importance of analyzing the effects of environmental interaction on deviant actors and its changes (dynamic view of crime), and identifies the basic key criminogenic explanations to crime causation (mechanistic view of crime). The theory postulated three basic explanatory techniques or mechanisms which are; situational, selection, and emergence. But believes that the actual causes of crime and deviance are situational; this forms the core of the theory Wikström (2012). This informed the researcher on the need to restrict himself to adopting the second axiom (The Situational Mechanism Model), as it possesses the capacity to present pivotal explanations to the research problems.

The Situational mechanism model or PEA hypothesis is the core of Situational Action Theory. The theory gives explanations for why crimes eventually happen. Wikström (2018) asserted:

“People ultimately commit acts of crime because they find them acceptable in the circumstance (and

there is no relevant and strong enough deterrent) or because they fail to act in accordance with their own personal morals (i.e., fail to exercise self-control) in circumstances when externally pressurized to act otherwise. Therefore, the acts of crime are an outcome of the convergence of and interaction between people's crime propensities and places criminogenic inducements”.

Teenage Prostitution and the PEA hypothesis

The writer believes that for Wikström (2018) to present a more scientific explanation to its model, he developed a formula known as, The PEA hypothesis ($P \times E \rightarrow A$) maintained that an act of deviance (teenage Prostitution) (A) is as a

Figure 1. The illustration of Situational Action Theory (SAT)

Source: Wikström, 2018

The situations might reflect the circumstances of family conditions defined in terms of weak socio-economic status position. This might propel parents wanting to give their children away to others who wish to give assistance in return for training the child and granting other socio-psycho support through attachment. Some of the pressures emanating from the socio-economic status position of families might take the form of poverty, lack of socio-psychological support and guidance, due to parent's job career, occupational background. More so, environmental factors triggered by where one lives or associations children keeps, reflecting peer influences and pressures. All these situations are likely to possess strong impact factor that pushes the child to engage in teenage prostitution.

The theory tried to give an explanation using the variable 'situations, but failed to explain why

result of perceptive-choice pattern (intrinsic motive) (\rightarrow) initiated and guided by the interaction (extrinsic) (\times) between an individual's propensities to commit crime (the teenager's ability and capacity) (P) and the actor's environment's criminogenic inducements (family, social influences, and criminogenic factors) (E) in response to a specific motivation (Pressure, either intrinsic or extrinsic). Thus, the act of deviance (teenage prostitution) is an outcome of specific combinations of certain kinds of individuals' propensities and environmental inducements.

The Action Process Steps

most prostitutes don't want to relinquish the profession even if they are offered better job opportunities. This might be a result of full adjustment and adaptation due to years of pleasure-seeking behavior while in the profession. Thus, this should be an eye-opener for subsequent theorists and researchers to postulate a more generally sophisticated theory that can adequately and explicitly address those identified cases.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to investigate family pressure, peer influence, and teenagers' involvement in prostitution in Delta State. Specifically, we sought to determine the influence of:

1. Family pressure on teenagers' involvement in prostitution

2. Peer influence and teenagers' involvement in prostitution
3. Family pressure and teenagers' involvement in prostitution

Research Hypotheses

The state null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 levels of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between family pressure and teenager's involvement in prostitution.
2. There is no significant relationship between peer influence and teenagers' involvement in prostitution.
3. Family pressure and peer influence will not jointly predict a teenager's involvement in prostitution.

Research Method

The study was carried out using both quantitative and qualitative research. An ex post facto research design and in-depth Interviews (IDIs) were used for the study. The study area was Delta State. Due to the nature of the job, teenager prostitution, it was not possible to have a registered number of teenagers involved in it, except for the ones found in the street at night and in brothels. The target population for the study was teenagers between the ages of 15 and

18 found in some brothels, on the street at night, and in guest houses involved in prostitution as a way of surviving a hard time. The sample size is 120 teenagers. The questionnaire was developed by the researcher and validated by experts in the field of measurement and evaluation. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled Parental Pressure, Peer Influence, and Teenagers Involvement in Prostitution (PPPITIPP), which has two parts: Part A deals with demographics such as age, gender, and location, while Part B contains two sections dealing with parental pressures on teenager prostitution and another section dealing with peer influence on teenager prostitution. Both instruments have a reliability of 0.78 and 0.85, respectively. An in-depth interview was conducted with six respondents; this was made possible by the participant observation method adopted by the research. A photograph was taken. A semi-structured interview guide was used for the IDI. The researcher transcribed the data acquired from the In-depth interviews through the use of a recording device, and they were compared with the notes taken by the note-taker during the meetings. Both the transcribed tapes and the field notes were used for data analysis. Simple regression was used to test the first two hypotheses, and multiple regression was used for the last hypothesis, as well as content analysis for the In-depth interview.

Figure 2. Field Photo of Teenagers at Guest House. Photograph Taken During the In-Depth Interview

Findings from In-Depth Interview

Does Family pressure lead to teenager involvement in prostitution?

First respondent said:

My parent nor know say na prostitution, dem carry me come do for here. Family pressure, no food to eat, no school I dey go. Na for street hawking I take see the madam, wen bring me come here, I be nor wan come but my parents put pressure say if I get better work for city which the madam promise them, I go fit dey send like 70k come home twice in a month. Oga, I nor go lie give you, life too hard, na my body be my workshop now. I don sacrifice myself for the progress of my family. I go only stop this work, whenever I decide to. (IDI/Female/17 years)

Second Respondent

Well am an orphan, I don't know my father, but lost my mother when I was very young, no member of my mother's family cared for me due to the hard life they were facing too, at age 12, I started sleeping with men to survival in the town, and the money I make, I still give little to fed my caregivers children. Bros, my eyes are red, I don't know to remember those days anymore, just come make we go inside to enjoy yourself make you pay me. Time dey go, na rush hour be this. Every week, I send money home to care for my child when I born, when I be 14 years. (IDI/Female/16 years).

Third Respondents

oga, hope you are not planning to arrest us, my mother have be hearing rumours from people in village that I am doing prostitution in the city, that I am not working in any factory, they promised her before I was released leave the village. See my phone, see text message of urgent financial need. Oga, I do I help them? if not for this business, even people wen finish university too still dey here

dey hustle for money to pay bills on a daily basis. (IDI/Female/17 years).

Does peer influence lead to teenager involvement in prostitution?

Fourth Respondent

Hope you nor be police? E get where person go help you reach, and you know say, na runs (ashowo) the person dey do, you nor get choice again but to join the business and pray make you nor run out of luck. Na code I take dey do the business, i only do short service, (IDI/Female/17 years)

Fifth Respondent

Though my peers deceived me into this business at first, I am seeing how lucrative it is and you can protect yourself if you stick to the rules, always use condom, nor sleep man house for money. After being into this business for some time now, I can comfortable afford anything my peers have now, unlike before, when I used to wear one pant for three days, no pad for monthly circle. (IDI/Female/16years)

Sixth Respondent

I will not really say my peers influence me into this business; I grow up in a surrounding where ladies trade their body for money. I already have that consciousness that when things are difficulty for me, I will used prostitution to raise money to finance any project I have at hand, I am currently saving fund to start up my fashion business. Few months from now I will be 18, though, I have being in this business for two year and I have a son. (IDI/Female/17years).

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between family pressure and teenagers' involvement in prostitution.

Table Group 1. Linear Regression on Relationship Between Family Pressure and Teenager Involvement in Prostitution

Table 1a. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.197 ^a	.039	.031	4.794

Table 1b. ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	109.168	1	109.168	4.751	.031 ^b
	Residual	2711.424	118	22.978		
	Total	2820.592	119			

Table 1c. Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	37.694	1.494		25.226	.000
	Family Pressure	.091	.042	.197	2.180	.031

Table group 1 reveals an F value of 4.751 and a p value of .031 testing at an alpha level of 0.05; the p value is less than the alpha level, so the null hypothesis, which states that "There is no significant relationship between family pressure and teenager involvement in prostitution, is rejected. The result reveals that family pressure significantly relates to teenager involvement in prostitution. From the table, independent variables made a significant contribution to the

prediction of teenagers' involvement in prostitution. It accounted for 19.7% of the total variance in teenager involvement in prostitution (B = .197, t = 2.180, p = .031 < 0.05). It was significant at the 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between peer influence and teenage involvement in prostitution.

Table Group 2. Linear Regression of the Relationship Between Peer Influence and Teenagers' Involvement in Prostitution**Table 2a. Model Summary**

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.236 ^a	.056	.048	4.751

Table 2b. ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	157.333	1	157.333	6.971	.009 ^b
	Residual	2663.259	118	22.570		
	Total	2820.592	119			

Table 2c. Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	28.649	4.626		6.193	.000
	Peer Influence	.279	.106	.236	2.640	.009

Table group 2 reveals an F value of 6.971 and a p value of .009 testing at an alpha level of 0.05; the p value is less than the alpha level. Therefore, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no

significant relationship between peer influence and teenage involvement in prostitution, is rejected. The result of the analysis showed that there is a relationship between peer influence

and teenage involvement in prostitution. The table also shows the model summary showing the relationship between peer influence and teenage involvement in prostitution. The result yielded a regression coefficient of .236; a coefficient of multiple determination of .056; and an adjusted R-square of .048. It indicates that peer influence significantly relates to teenagers' involvement in prostitution. The r^2 value of .056

shows that 5.6% of variance in peer influence accounted for teenager involvement in prostitution. The standardized coefficient (B) = .236; $t = 2.640$; $p = .0009$. Thus, peer influence is significant at a P-value of 0.05.

Hypothesis 3: Family pressure and peer influence will not significantly predict a teenager's involvement in prostitution.

Table Group 3. Multiple Regression Analysis Showing Family Pressure and Peer Influence on Teenager Involvement in Prostitution

Table 3a. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.290 ^a	.084	.069	4.699

Table 3b. ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	237.543	2	118.772	5.380	.006 ^b
	Residual	2583.049	117	22.077		
	Total	2820.592	119			

Table 3c. Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	27.048	4.652		5.815	.000
	Family Pressure	.079	.041	.170	1.906	.049
	Peer Influence	.254	.105	.215	2.411	.017

Table group 3 shows an F value of 5.380 and a p value of .006 testing at an alpha level of 0.05. The p value is less than the alpha level, so the null hypothesis, which states that "There is no significant relationship between family pressure and teenager involvement in prostitution, is rejected. The result reveals that family pressure significantly relates to teenager involvement in prostitution. From the table, the two independent variables made a significant contribution to the prediction of teenager involvement in prostitution. Peer influence was the best predictor of prostitution. It accounted for 21.5% of the total variance in internet fraud (B = -.215, $t = 2.411$, $p = .017 < 0.05$). Family pressure was the least predictive. Although it accounted for 17% of teenager involvement in prostitution, it was also significant at the 0.05

level of significance (B = .170, $t = 1.906$, $p = 0.049 < 0.05$).

Discussion

The findings from the first hypothesis reveal that family pressure significantly predicts teenage involvement in prostitution. This implies that family pressure may manifest in the form of parents not being able to cater for their children by sending their ward to live with those who promise to help them with jobs, not knowing the teenager is involved in prostitution for survival. As a result, some girls have been forced to use prostitution to feed themselves. It is very common these days in many Nigerian cities to see some young girls roaming the streets and hotels seeking clients when they are supposed to be in school or at home. This finding is in

agreement with Maria's (2022) finding that many young women and girls fall prey to pressure from poverty in their families, that is, the inability to meet the basic needs of the female child, and have been deceived by relatives who promise to help them train their female child in the city. Ampofo (2022) justifies such a point by saying that the lack of economic and financial support from close relatives has forced teenagers to finally engage in prostitution. Similarly, the macroeconomic shifts and changes that cause economic constraints have also accelerated women's willingness to work as prostitutes.

The second finding pointed out that there is a relationship between peer influence and teenage involvement in prostitution. This may mean that peer influence may influence teenagers to be involved in prostitution, but it is not a causative factor strong enough to conclude that it led to teenagers commercializing their bodies for sex. Also, teenagers involved in prostitution do it at their own peril because they want to be like their friends at all costs. This finding is in consonance with the work of Olufemi and Olasunkanmi (2015) as well as Izugbara (2010), who report that peer group influence, influence from the environment, lack of opportunity, and early sexual experience largely predispose women and girls to prostitution as an occupation to survive life's realities. Olugbile (2008) wrote that peer influence is everywhere, where everyone wants to be like others and ends up prostituting. The bad girls who embrace prostitution gradually corrupt the more conservative ones. If, for example, one person had three cell phones and flashy clothes, another would want to do the same or more. For those who are probably not from very rich homes, they are forced to do otherwise.

The result also indicated that the result reveals that family pressure significantly relates to teenager involvement in prostitution. From the table, the two independent variables made a significant contribution to the prediction of teenager involvement in prostitution. Peer influence was the best predictor of prostitution. The findings support the work of Yusuf (2013), who found that there is an increase in teenage prostitution and sex-related activities among

young people due to the inability of parents to meet their financial obligations. Parents may be compelled to send their female child to individuals who promise to train and educate them in return not knowing the child will be forced into prostitution.

Conclusion

Inferring from the various findings, the study concluded that peer influences are a major variable that propel teenagers into prostitution, and a lack of economic power has put strains on parents to send their girl child to the city in the name of searching for a greener pasture, who end up becoming prostitutes.

Research Recommendations

The following recommendations were put forward;

1. Parents should take full responsibility for the upbringing of their children and should desist from giving their children economic favors from friends and relatives. In most cases, such children end up becoming prostitutes and armed robbers.
2. Female children should be taught moral values based on the principles of contentment and hard work and not see peer comparison and wanting to belong to a class of friends who are already into teenage prostitution as a do-or-die approach to life success.

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